

Modifying Infill Settings to Optimize the Conductivity and Tensile Strength of 3D Printed Parts After Copper Electroplating

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Abstract

Fused filament fabrication (FFF) 3D printing is widely used within both hobbyist and industrial applications for its superior printing speed and cost-effectiveness in comparison to other conventional technologies, such as fused deposition modeling. Some of the drawbacks of FFF technology, however, include the limited electrical conductivity and mechanical strength of its parts. The purpose of this research, therefore, is to improve the electrical conductivity and mechanical strength of FFF parts by optimizing the infill parameters used in the printing process in conjunction with performing a copper electroplating of the parts. This was done by fabricating 3D prints at varying infill densities, which were then coated with a conductive paint and electroplated with copper. It was found that the electroplated parts had higher UTS values ($p < 0.01$) and lower resistances ($p < 0.01$), and that the magnitude of change in resistance and UTS values also increased across infill densities following electrolysis ($p < 0.05$). These results reflect the viability of accessible materials in optimizing the conductivity and mechanical strength of 3D prints, thus expanding industrial applicability of additive manufacturing in areas including rapid-prototyping.

Keywords: 3D Printing, Additive Manufacturing, Electroplating, Electrodeposition, Electrochemistry

1. Introduction

3D printing, also known as additive manufacturing, is a multibillion-dollar international industry (Ślusarczyk, 2021). with applications in the automotive, robotics, and aerospace industries. A primary drawback of current 3D printing technologies, however, is their limited electrical applicability. Modern 3D printing filaments, which are primarily composed of ABS and PLA plastics, are highly resistive and bear a low electrical conductivity due to the innately insulating nature of plastic. A new development in this field, however, is the use of electroplating, the deposition of metal onto a substrate material via the supply of an electrical current, to improve the electrical conductivity and other functional properties of a 3D printed part.

1.1 Electroplating efficacy

In recent years, much of the work in the field of electroplating 3D prints has been focused on utilizing commercially accessible conductive filaments to improve plating success as measured by adhesion strength, electrodeposition quality, and surface texture. A 2017 study focused on electroplating a print made from conductive PLA filament to better the part's conductivity found that electroplating achieved optimal efficiency when performed laterally, while performing the electroplating with higher voltages typically resulted in higher resistances and thus lower conductivities (Kadari et al., 2017). Similarly, a 2019 study conducted research on different types of commercially available conductive filaments and properties such as surface roughness, conductivity, and quality for each of the 3 tested conductive PLA filaments (Electrifi®, Black Magic®, Proto-Pasta®) (Kim et al., 2019). The study found that the initial resistances of each of the tested filaments were lowered as a result of electroplating. Also, while each filament had its own optimal printing speed and temperature for minimal electrical resistance, the Proto-Pasta® filament maintained relatively uniform electrodeposition while being the among the lowest priced conductive filaments currently available for consumer purchase (Jangid et al., 2022). It is for this reason that the Proto-Pasta® conductive PLA was used in the present study: a balance of both availability and functionality is paramount for the purposes of optimizing industrial viability.

1.2 Electronic applications

The recent increase in research and data on the electroplating of 3D prints has allowed for the research to be applied in fields relating to technology and electrical engineering. While a variety of 3D printing filaments have been studied with respect to electronic applications, those tested by Kim et al., in addition to select others, have been extensively tested with respect to electronics due to their consumer accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and performance. The relatively narrow scope of currently studied filaments has allowed researchers to gain a detailed understanding of how certain commercially available filaments perform in scenarios such as in use within circuits and other electronic devices. One such example of this development is a 2017 study that explored how FFF printing can employ certain conductive filaments to create a variety of functional resistors, inductors, and capacitors (Flowers et al., 2017). The conductive filaments employed included traditional, carbon-based filaments in addition to a bronze-filled PLA; the study's results detailed how the conductive filaments can be applied in devices such as wireless power transfer circuits and a high-pass filter. As such, the practical and industry-focused applications of functionalized parts fabricated through additive manufacturing were elucidated, paving the way for other functionalization techniques, such as electroplating, to be explored.

1.3 Mechanical applications

In addition to the electrodeposition of copper onto 3D printing filaments, several research studies have also detailed the applicability of metal-PLA composites: readily accessible metal-integrated PLA plastics that bear properties similar to both PLA plastics and pure metals. Due to their consumer availability, metal-PLA filaments are optimal models for predicting and estimating the performance and functionalization success of electroplating processes involving copper and similar metals. Multiple recent studies have underscored the mechanical performance of Cu-PLA composites, specifically, citing their blend of plastic's light weight with

copper's ductility as a beneficial combination for many mechanically demanding loads, including flexural and compression tests (Kesavarama et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2019). It was reported that, for 25% and 80% by weight Cu-PLA composite filaments, the 25% by weight composite had higher flexural strength, while the 80% by weight composite had a higher flexural modulus; the high copper composition reduced the strength but increased the composite stiffness. A related study also explored the variance of printing parameters as it related to the optimization and modification of Cu-PLA composites' mechanical performance: compression and flexural tests revealed that increasing nozzle and bed temperatures improved the compression and flexural strengths of the printed parts of a 14% by weight Cu composite (Balamurugan et al., 2021). The recent investigation of Cu-PLA composites presents the groundwork for similar work involving electroplating to be carried out, potentially serving as a point of comparison in the broader landscape of 3D printing functionalization applications.

1.4 Overview of work

The research centrally focuses on the improvement of a 3D print's electrical properties via the modulation of its printing parameters and through electroplating. Prior research has discussed the decreased resistance of a 3D print after it has been electroplated (Angel et al., 2018), and the proposed research will similarly conduct electroplating in order to better quantify the success of the plating process and determine the effects that printing parameters' variance have on the plated part's electrical properties. This study aims to contribute to the current body of knowledge on additive manufacturing by researching a new method by which FFF prints can have their electrical properties improved: the varying of infill parameters in conjunction with electroplating. The filament utilized in the study, the ProtoPasta® Conductive PLA, is among the cheapest and most widely-accessible conductive filaments currently available and was thus chosen for use within the study as opposed to more readily conductive filaments from Electrifi® or Black Magic® in order to broaden both the industrial and hobbyist applicability of the recorded findings. The specific infill parameter modified was infill density, or the amount of plastic printed within the interior of a 3D print. It was hypothesized that prints with small gaps in their infill will yield greater increases in electrical performance (less resistance) post-electroplating when compared to prints with more dense infill due to the better coverage of metal on the substrate; by increasing infill density, a greater surface area of the part will be exposed, and thus electroplating efficacy is hypothesized to improve. The basis of this study lies in the fact that it incorporates two moderately studied additive manufacturing concepts, printing parameter variance and electroplating, and observes their combined result on the final material's electrical properties. These experiments will pave the way for the novel applications of stronger, more useful, and functionalized parts fabricated through additive manufacturing techniques to be applied in industry; such developments could potentially reduce the cost and time associated with large scale manufacturing processes. Section 2 of this paper presents the materials and methods with which the data, as presented and analyzed in Section 3 of this paper, were collected. Section 4 represents a concise description of the study's overall findings and implications on future work.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Printing procedure

Using the Fusion 360® software, a CAD model was created based off a typical ASTM® tensile strength model (Figure 1) (4.5cm length, 0.475cm width, 0.08cm height) and it was then imported into the PrusaSlicer 2.5® slicing software to be prepared for printing (ASM International, 2004).

Figure 1. Image of 3D printing model used (from slicing software)

Within the slicer, the “Line” (linear) infill pattern was selected along with 20, 30, and 40 percent infill densities; 10 models of each density were printed for a total of 30 3D prints. Once the slicer file was appropriately modified, it was saved as a “.gcode” file and then it was saved onto a flash drive which was inserted within the Prusa MINI+® 3D printer. Using the ProtoPasta® Conductive PLA filament, 3 different 3D printing configurations were fabricated using the Prusa MINI+® printer and each configuration was repeated ten times, for a total of 30 prints: 15 experimental (electroplated) units and 15 control (non-electroplated) units. Thus, 5 repeated trials were taken for each measurement, or electroplating and infill combination. After feeding the filament into the 3D printer, which was carried out by selecting the “Load Filament” option in the printer’s GUI and selecting “PLA,” the extruder temperature was set to 488 K (215°C) whilst the print bed temperature was set to 333 K (60°C) (standard Prusa MINI+® PLA settings). The 3D printer was operated in a well-ventilated area and a safe distance was maintained from the printing bed to prevent any heat-related injuries. Fabricated parts were handled delicately during removal from the print bed and were ensured to be fully dry prior to removal to ensure that injuries and damage to the samples were prevented. A sample printed part with an infill density of 30% and linear infill pattern can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Image of fabricated 3D print prior to electroplating

2.2 Electroplating process

To prep the parts for electroplating, all the initially fabricated 3D prints were painted with a conductive, nickel-based paint (MG Chemicals 841AR®). Each 3D print was fully submerged within a container of the paint for 10s and allowed to drip excess liquid off before the parts were allowed to dry for 24hrs at 294 K (21°C). Each part was coated with a single coat of the conductive paint and was dried upon a paper towel.

An electroplating setup was created involving a 250mL beaker filled with 9g Copper (II) Sulfate Pentahydrate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 90mL H_2O , and 22.5mL 1M Sulfuric Acid. When handling acids, PPE including gloves, lab coats, and goggles was worn. The anode (pure copper strip, ~99% Cu) was connected to the Elenco

XP-605®, a DC power supply which was connected to the cathode (the 3D print) using alligator clips. An image of the experimental setup used is shown in Figure 3: the red cable, representing the positive terminal, is attached to the substrate/cathode while the yellow cable, representing the ground terminal, is attached to the copper/anode.

Figure 3. Image of electroplating setup

After allowing the cell to run for 40s at a voltage of 4V and a variable current (roughly 0.1A), the cathode was removed from the beaker and air dried on a paper towel until no liquid remained on the part. It is important to note that the substrate was turned during the plating process such that each of the 2 large faces of the print faced the copper during the process (20s for each of the large faces, for a total of 40s) and the substrate was held 6cm from the copper. Additionally, the electroplating setup was operated within a well-ventilated area in order to dissipate toxic fumes (Safe Work Australia, 2012). After electroplating, parts were placed upon a sheet of paper for 2hrs at 294 K (21°C) until fully dry. Figure 4 depicts the appearance of the plated and painted samples.

Figure 4. From top to bottom: painted and electroplated sample, painted and non-plated sample

2.3 Electrical and mechanical testing

After electroplating half of the 30 initially fabricated 3D prints, all 30 3D prints were employed for use in a multimeter (Cen-Tech 61593 11 Function Multimeter®) where the maximum resistance was set to 200Ω ; the positive and negative leads of the multimeter were placed in the two ends of each 3D print (within the parts' infill) and the resulting resistance value was recorded. It was ensured that the value recorded was one that was not significantly fluctuating at the time of measurement in order to ensure the accuracy of recorded values. Figure 5 depicts the multimeter setup used.

Figure 5. Image of multimeter setup

After the test for electrical resistance, each of the 30 parts were employed within a Mark-10 F305® tensile strength machine and the amount of force endured by each part before the point where the part breaks or cleaves (ultimate tensile strength, UTS) was recorded. The part must be placed between the two grips of the machine such that the curved edges of the part are placed within the grips. An image of the experimental setup involving the tensile strength machine and test sample can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Image of Tensile Strength Machine Setup (3D printed sample placed between metal clamps)

The units of force were measured in Newtons (N) and the machine was set to a travel speed of 254mm/min. Data collection was programmed with the Intelli-MESUR® software to pause and record the UTS when a large drop of strain was recorded (cleavage point).

3. Results and Discussion

This study aimed to quantify the amount by which electroplated 3D printed parts can be optimized for industrial usage and mechanical/electrical performance via the variance of infill parameters. Through analyzing the electrical resistance and ultimate tensile strengths of several sets of fabricated 3D prints using statistical significance tests, it was found that denser infills yielded superior improvements to mechanical and electrical performance (lower resistances and higher tensile strengths).

3.1 Statistical and quantitative metrics

Table 1 represents the varying electrical resistance values for the fabricated 3D prints of a given infill density with a constant (linear) infill pattern prior to copper electroplating.

Table 1. Infill Densities and Resistances of Non-Electroplated 3D Prints

Infill Density (%)	Electrical Resistance (Ω)					Average
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	
20	5.3	9.4	8.7	9	9.5	8.4
30	12	7.1	8.2	7.2	4.7	7.8
40	4	5.6	5	6	5.5	5.2

Table 2 represents the varying electrical resistance values for the fabricated 3D prints of a given infill density, but for parts that were plated with copper and allowed to appropriately dry.

Table 2. Infill Densities and Resistances of Electroplated 3D Prints

Infill Density (%)	Electrical Resistance (Ω)					Average
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	
20	10.3	5	6.5	6.2	6.8	7
30	7.2	6.6	6.4	5.2	7.7	6.6
40	2	3.1	2.2	2.7	1.8	2.4

Table 3 represents the varying UTS values for the fabricated 3D prints of a given infill density with a constant (linear) infill pattern prior to copper electroplating.

Table 3. Infill Densities and Ultimate Tensile Strengths of Non-Electroplated 3D Prints

Infill Density (%)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (N)					
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Average
20	36.4	36.5	31.5	41.5	38.5	36.9
30	37.5	37.1	36.8	40.8	38.3	38.1
40	48	48.3	51.5	40	41.5	45.9

Table 4 represents the varying UTS values for the fabricated 3D prints of a given infill density, but for parts that were plated with copper and allowed to appropriately dry.

Table 4. Infill Densities and Ultimate Tensile Strengths of Electroplated 3D Prints

Infill Density (%)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (N)					
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Average
20	42	42.3	42.5	40.5	37.5	41
30	41.8	41.1	42.8	43.2	42.3	42.2
40	54.2	55.8	51.6	54.3	52.2	53.6

To quantify the amount by which varying infill density affected the electrical and mechanical performance of the electroplated 3D prints, a Kruskal-Wallis statistical test, along with the associated Dunn's post-hoc test, were conducted using the InStat[®] statistical analysis software (GraphPad[®], USA). A non-parametric analysis was employed as the dataset lacked enough data points to qualify a parametric study by means of the ANOVA and Tukey post-hoc tests.

Table 5. Resistances and Ultimate Tensile Strengths of 3D Prints with Differing Infill Densities Post-Electroplating

	Electrical (Resistance)	Mechanical (Ultimate Tensile Strength)
KW-Statistic	9.42	9.875
df (degrees of freedom)	2	2
p-value	0.009	0.007

With a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $df = 2$, the calculated Kruskal-Wallis test statistics (KW-Statistic) were found to be equal to 9.420 (resistances) and 9.875 (tensile strengths), while the calculated p-

values was found to be 0.009 (resistances) and 0.007 (tensile strengths) (see Table 5). With the obtained p-value being less than the established significance level, the difference between the resistances and UTS values of the parts with differing infills were established, and a post-hoc test was subsequently conducted to identify which groups (infill density levels) differ from the others in terms of mechanical/electrical performance.

Table 6. Comparisons Across Infill Densities for Resistances and Ultimate Tensile Strengths of 3D Prints with Differing Infill Densities Post-Electroplating

Infill Density Comparison	p-value	
	Resistance	Ultimate Tensile Strength
20% vs. 30%	0.832	0.296
20% vs. 40%	0.001	0.009
30% vs. 40%	0.006	0.009

From the post-hoc test's results (see Table 6), a significant difference between the parts' resistances and UTS values post-electroplating was identified in the comparison between the 30% and 40% infill densities ($p\text{-value}=0.006 < \alpha$ for resistances, $p\text{-value}=0.009 < \alpha$ for tensile strengths), as well as the 20% and 40% infill densities ($p\text{-value}=0.001 < \alpha$ for resistances, $p\text{-value}=0.009 < \alpha$ for tensile strengths). The comparison involving the 20% and 30% infill densities was not identified to have a significant difference in the parts' infills ($p\text{-value}=0.832 > \alpha$, $p\text{-value}=0.009 < \alpha$ for tensile strengths). Such a difference may suggest that an increase in infill density is not directly proportional to the amount by which electroplating effectiveness, as quantified by a decrease in resistance and increase in UTS, is improved.

Figure 7. Relationship Between Resistance and Infill Density for Electroplated and Non-Electroplated Parts over Varying Infill Densities

Figure 8. Relationship Between Ultimate Tensile Strength and Infill Density for Electroplated and Non-Electroplated Parts over Varying Infill Densities

In Figure 7, the error bars displayed are 10% of the resistance value in length, and their minimal overlap between the two plotted curves, especially at the higher infill densities, represents the distinction between these two curves' represented values and thus the significance of electroplating's effect on resistance. In Figure 8, although the 10% error bars have significant overlap, the general trend of both the electroplated and non-electroplated graphs are quite similar, indicating that the effect of electroplating on the 3D prints' mechanical properties are minimal, yet consistent across infill densities. While the larger slope/curvature of the curves in Figure 7 reflects that conductivity increases rapidly as infill density increases, the smaller slope/curvature in Figure 8's plots reflect that increasing infill density of electroplated 3D prints only yields small, incremental improvements to mechanical performance.

To relate the present study's findings with those of previous research, the pre-electroplating and post-electroplating data for each infill density tested was compared using a one-tailed Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($\alpha = 0.05$), shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Improvements of Resistances and Ultimate Tensile Strengths of 3D Prints Before and After Electroplating for Single Infill Densities

Infill Density	% Improvement After Electroplating	
	Resistance	Ultimate Tensile Strength
20%	17	11
30%	16	11*
40%	54*	17*

* Denotes statistical significance ($p < 0.05$)

3.2 Merits

The general improvement in electroplating efficacy as infill density increases underscores the conclusions of previous studies that claim for electroplating to be increasingly effective with denser infills (Kannan et al., 2014). As seen in Table 7, both UTS and resistance increase as infill density increases. Furthermore, the significant differences between electroplated and non-electroplated data for both UTS values and resistances at higher infills can be attributed to the nature of chemical bonding and electrodeposition at the atomic scale; as more surface area, or infill material, is presented within a given sample for copper metal atoms to bond upon, a greater number of metal atoms will adhere to the 3D printed substrate post-electroplating. As a result, the resulting material, an electroplated 3D print, will bear more metallic properties if a larger number of metal atoms can bond to its surface (Kannan & Senthilkumaran, 2014). Since copper and many other metals bear superior electrical conductivities and tensile properties in comparison to plastics due to their unique delocalized electron structure (“electron sea” bonding), plastics plated with metal gain improvements to their electrical conductivity and mechanical strength.

The data collected as part of this research largely corroborate with previous studies regarding the functionalization of 3D prints via electrodeposition processes as it elucidates the process’s improvements of mechanical and electrical performance (Kumar et al., 2015). Within the experiments conducted, an electrolyte solution similar to that which was used in previous studies was used in order to maximize the conducted experiments’ broad applicability (Angel et al., 2018). Additionally, the primary materials utilized within the fabrication processes, the carbon-based conductive filament and conductive paint, were chosen as they are both commercially available, can be purchased in bulk for relatively low prices, and have had their implications on the functionalization process explored in the past (Kumar et al., 2015). Such choices made in the experimental process underscore the validity, replicability, and significance of the acquired results.

3.3 Limitations and improvements

Experimental limitations involved in the study can be associated with inconsistencies caused by the drying and resistance measurement processes as they relate to the fabricated parts’ infills. As illustrated in Figure 2, not all cross-links established within a given part’s infill are connected with each other as theoretically modeled in Figure 1. Consequently, certain connections of the fabricated parts’ infills may be incomplete or broken which would limit electrical conductivity since electrons would be unable to pass through the parts as theorized, increasing the resistance as determined by the multimeter. The impacts of similar inconsistencies can be mitigated via the use of a slower nozzle speed or higher nozzle temperature: the former would allow for more measured and precise movements of the nozzle thus minimizing possibility for the “skipping” of certain areas of infill while the latter would better liquify the filament, allowing for it to have better flow and less viscosity.

Additionally, while the parts were being employed within a multimeter for resistance measurements, it was observed that the infills within certain samples, especially those of a higher infill density, broke or cracked slightly during the measurement process. As a result, some of the cross-links of the parts were broken or displaced from their orientations prior to the measurements, impeding electron flow. In future work, a modification to the model depicted in Figure 1 can be made such that gaps within the CAD model are created to allow for the probes of a multimeter to rest, thus minimizing the possibility of damaging the samples.

3.4 Future work and implications

Recent work exploring applications of dual extruder printing, which involves the utilization of two, distinct filaments with separate extruders to fabricate a single print, has bolstered electroplating's future industrial viability via the implementation of selective electroplating. Such a process will allow for the development of other electronic components, such as more advanced circuitry, in the coming years; conductive elements can be fabricated with a metal or graphite-based filament while non-conductive components can be fabricated with traditional PLA/ABS for weight and cost effectiveness (Lazarus et al., 2019). The study sought to use 3D printing in tandem with a copper/PLA composite filament in order to create functional composite electrodes (Vaněčková et al., 2019). Researchers detailed how cyclic voltammetry was used in order to quantify the performance of manufactured electrodes; it was determined that the composite electrodes, which produced a negligible kinetic barrier and faradic responses comparable to pure metallic electrodes, obtained a peak faradaic separation indicative of a system with relatively unhindered electron flow as compared to standard metallic electrodes. With the rapid development of both the additive manufacturing and electronics industries in recent years (Ślusarczyk, 2021), 3D prints functionalized via electrodeposition may emerge as low-cost and widely accessible alternatives to fully metallic electrodes for use in a variety of electronics applications.

In the future, it will be important to determine how this research as well as similar work pertaining to 3D prints and polymeric materials contribute to the understanding of the rapidly developing field of porous metals. Porous metals, a group of materials that are lightweight and reactive yet maintain similar conductivity and ductility characteristics when compared with traditional metals, are promising for several applications including those in solar energy and combustion systems (Rashidi et al., 2017; Gharehghani et al., 2021). The study of this unique class of materials has been limited to costly and time-consuming studies until recently, and the use of electroplating within this research is especially important: it is posited that 3D printing post-fabrication functionalization techniques, which deal with porous materials, can be adapted to also broaden the applicability of porous metals, given the two material classes' similarities in structure (Orbulov, 2021).

4. Conclusion

The findings of this research demonstrate that infill density and the mechanical and electrical performance of electroplated 3D printed parts are generally inversely proportional, although the exact relationship between the variables remains to be explored. As evidenced by the statistical analyses carried out, a variance of infill density does impact resistance and UTS in a statistically significant manner for electroplated parts, thus expanding the possibilities and potential uses of 3D printed parts within industries such as consumer electronics and circuit manufacturing. With the configurability, cost-effectiveness, and lightweight qualities that electroplated 3D prints offer in relation to alternatives such as pure metals or alloys, their widespread applicability is clear. Furthermore, this research has been adapted to be easily scalable or replicable at a low cost, as the filament, 3D printer, and electroplating setup, while adapted from earlier studies, are all commercially available for a fraction of the price of industrial-grade equipment.

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Siddarth Sreeram – A researcher at the Academies of Loudoun from Virginia, USA, Siddarth is deeply interested in investigating and elucidating the industrial applications of commonly studied electrochemical processes. Siddarth pursues and has completed a wide variety of independent and collaborative research projects relating to the fields of electrochemistry, materials engineering, and polymer chemistry.